

DOI

Jurakulova D.Sh.
student
Daminova M.I.
student
Alikulov O.A.
student
faculty of Dentistry
Samarkand State Medical University
Uzbekistan

ROLE OF HYPNOSIS IN DENTAL TREATMENT

Abstract. Hypnosis is a physiological mind activity characterized by focused attention, absorption, dissociation and plastic imagination. In the early 19th century, several hundred surgical interventions were described with hypnosis as the sole anesthetic, in an epoch when no anesthetic drugs were available; then hypnosis was prejudicially abandoned and forgotten after its introduction. In the past two decades, an increasing number of studies on hypnosis has shown its capacity to modify the activity of the prefrontal cortex, default mode network and pain neuromatrix (including the anterior cingulate cortex, amygdala, thalamus, insula and somatosensory cortex) and increase pain threshold up to the level of surgical anesthesia.

Keywords: Hypnosis, Hypnotic analgesia, Clinic hypnosis, anxiety and phobia.

Hypnotic analgesia also prevents pain-related cardiovascular response: therefore, it may stand comparison with pharmacological anesthesia, yielding true protection from stress for the patient. The wealth of data available in the literature provides clear evidence of its meaningful effects on perioperative emotional distress, pain, medication consumption, physiological parameters, duration of surgery and outcome. Hypnosis may be used as follows: 1) as sole anesthetic, in minor surgery and invasive maneuvers and/or selected patients; 2) as adjuvant of pharmacological anesthesia (local anesthesia and/or sedation); 3) as an adjuvant technique in both pre- and postoperative phases in patients submitted to general anesthesia.

Hypnosis, unlike any other therapeutic tools, does not call for drugs or equipment and is an attractive technique: it is free of charge, not burdened with proved adverse events and promises to help improving cost/benefits ratio.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

The application of hypnosis in dentistry includes several types of comfortability for patient and for high skilled doctors. A psychological method called Clinic hypnosis teaches dentists to use this tool for many beneficial purposes.

For instance:

- Relaxation
- Anxiety control
- Control of Bruxism (grinding of teeth)
- Gag reflex reduction
- Pain control
- Anesthesia
- Reduction of bleeding and swelling
- Improvement of oral hygiene habits
- More rapid comfortable healing
- Adjustment to oral appliances

In Conclusion, Hypnosis is a valuable tool in dentistry, enabling the safe and rapid relief of anxiety and phobia and raising patient pain thresholds to the level of surgical analgesia. Unlike drugs and equipment, it is always readily available, cost-free, and has no adverse effects when administered by competent professionals.

References:

1. Dionne RA, Gordon SM, McCullagh LM, Phero JC. Assessing the need for anesthesia and sedation in the general population. J Am Dent Assoc. 1998;129(2):167-173
2. Chanpong B, Haas DA, Locker D. Need and demand for sedation or general anesthesia in dentistry: a national survey of the Canadian population. Anesth Prog. 2005;52 (1):3-11
3. Oosterink FM, de Jongh A, Hoogstraten J. Prevalence of dental fear and phobia relative to other fear and phobia subtypes. Eur J Oral Sci. 2009;117(2):135-143.
4. Solana K. ADA House of Delegates adopts revisions in sedation, anesthesia guidelines. ADA News. November 7, 2016.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

<http://www.ada.org/en/publications/ada-news/2016-archive/november/ada-house-of-delegates-adopts-revisions-in-sedation-anesthesia-guidelines?source=redirect>. Accessed March 26, 2019.

5. American Dental Association. Guidelines for Teaching Pain Control and Sedation to Dentists and Dental Students. Ad-opted October 2012.

WORDLY
KNOWLEDGE